

Clinical Research Coordinator

Lucy Silonga (she/her)

"I love this job because it combines my passion for science with the ability to work with a wide array of great people."

Bio

For the past three years Lucy has worked as a clinical research coordinator, a demanding but fulfilling job. Working on around 4 investigators' projects, totaling 7 - 8 studies and clinical trials at any given time, Lucy's main charges are human subject protection and study management. Lucy devotes much of her time to study initiation, working with funders, regulatory agencies, and her institution's oversight committees to prepare regulatory documents, protocols, IRB submissions, and workflow documentation. She recruits and enrolls patients, helps them complete informed consents and documents this process for compliance with GCP, IRB, HIPAA, and other required funder or institutional policies. Making sure that all study procedures are in alignment with protocols, Lucy creates adverse events reports, keeps drug accountability documentation, oversees specimen transfers and processing, and performs continual quality assurance.

Lucy's teammates appreciate her knowledge and her mentoring work. They know she is a vital liaison between key research stakeholders including sponsors, regulatory bodies, PIs, patients, and clinical care organizations.

Education: BS, Biology

Years of experience: 3

Work location: Hospital, clinic sites, offices. Occasional remote work on her laptop

Goals

- A promotion to lead CRC
- Complete CRC Certification
- Delegate some tasks and build her skills in others
- Achieve a better work/life balance, reducing late-night and weekend work

Software attitude & use

- Embraces new technologies
- Feels proficient in the tools she uses at work but seeks to continually grow data curation skills in Excel
- Data security is paramount
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace, Adobe Acrobat
- Collaboration: citation management software, Box, Slack, Zoom
- Specialized resources: key web resources include those from the institutional IRB, NIH RePORTER, ClinicalTrials.gov, electronic medical record portals, supply and drug ordering websites, specimen processing software, and REDCap

Outputs

- Is occasionally attributed on investigators' publications for her role in data curation & analysis
- Produces guides to support routine clinical research workflows

Pain Points

- Lucy often feels overworked. Many of her studies require more time than first allotted
- Harmonizing disparate data
- Long wait times for collaborator responses on urgent issues
- Mobile versions of many software tools are sub-optimal

Motivators

- Solve health problems by working efficiently with key components and groups to complete studies
- Be thorough and transparent in her work and to document procedures for training, compliance, and accountability
- Coordinate accountable and reproducible science that ensures the safety of patients and security of their data

Wants/Needs

- More confidence in her work to know when she can suggest changes and improvements in data collection
- A delineation between her responsibilities and those of the investigators
- An understanding of when she can perform preliminary data analyses
- To delegate some of her tasks, such as ordering and preparing drugs, supplies, and testing kits for her unit
- A team approach to CRC work rather than single-PI assignment to best employ a CRC team's skills

Professional Development

Lucy wants CRC certification to fill any gaps in her knowledge of budgets, protocols, and working with sponsors

Lucy thrived with the peer mentorship she received when she started as a CRC, and she now mentors junior colleagues

Lucy gets new information for her role by talking to experienced colleagues, attending seminars, and following organizations like ACRP